

paper Chain

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Vestibulum	primis	faucibus	posuere	sollicitudin
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1 Introduction

The European pulp and paper sector accounts for a total paper and board production of 91 million tonnes, which represents the 22.2 % of the global production (CEPI, 2017). The pulp production reached 36,5 million tonnes and the paper used for recycling 47,6 million tonnes. The sector showed a continuous concentration, but means of a reduction of the number of companies, mills and paper machines, although this has not implied a reduction of the production and turnover, which remained stable or slightly higher.

	1991	2000	2005	2010	2015	2016
Number of Companies	1.032	929	831	675	636	623
Number of Mills	1.570	1.309	1.224	992	918	903
Number of Pulp Mills	296	233	218	172	155	153
Number of Paper and Board Mills	1.274	1.076	1.006	820	763	750
Number of Paper Machines	2.182	1.858	1.725	1.393	1.288	1.264
Turnover (Mill €)	n.a.	79.388	74.537	75.790	80.669	81.000
Pulp Production (K tonnes)	33.807	39.962	41.602	38.695	36.256	37.232
Paper and board production (K tonnes)	65.052	90.823	98.259	95.065	90.982	90.931

TABLE 1. GENERAL FIGURES OF THE EUROPEAN PULP AND PAPER SECTOR.

The sector has faced an optimization of the processes to gain competitiveness, leading to large facilities to benefit from the scale economy effect, with improved logistics, energy and materials efficiency. The materials efficiency includes actually the application of the waste hierarchy concept, preventing, reducing and recycling waste.

During the last decade, the sector has done a great effort to reduce landfilling and the rates of waste disposal, especially thanks to the energy recovery from wastes. Most of the new larger facilities have developed different systems to recover energy from different waste streams, usually by burning organic materials (sawdust, bark chips, paper rejects, sludge) in power boilers or even waste-to-energy facilities.

However, some other waste streams such as complex mixtures including organic and inorganic materials or the ashes generated in the different energy recovery systems are finding more problems to be completely recycled. The sectorial concentration produces more waste in one single point, which makes difficult for the local markets to absorb such amount of material, consequently, waste disposal still being a reality for most of the waste streams considered in the Paperchain project.

Thus, it is interesting to understand not only the details of the waste composition, characteristics and technical details of the proposed applications, but the distribution of the production. A better understanding of the waste producers' distributions, amounts of waste produced and details of the waste management will allow a further assessment on the economics of the waste valorization.

This report provides an overview on the numbers of the waste production in Europe by the pulp and paper industry, the regional distribution, type of waste and some general characteristics of the type of waste in a country-by-country basis. This compilation will be useful for the communication and dissemination activities and for the market analysis to be developed in WP8.

The data gathering on waste generation comes from several sources such as the national and European Pollutant Release Transfer Register (PRTR) at both European and national level. The national producers' associations or different statistical records have also been consulted, but in general, there is no homogenous way of presenting the information in Europe, and even there is frequently no obligation to declare the Non-hazardous waste production. Moreover, some waste streams are accounted but they are valorised generating other types of waste (for example sludge resulting into ash), introducing more uncertainty in some cases. Anyway, these figures must be interpreted as an approach for a better understanding and for an identification of opportunities for replication.

Finally, the document has been organised into three large geographic sectors: Nordic countries (Norway, Finland and Sweden), Central Europe and Balkan region (Poland, Italy, Germany, Austria, Czech Republic, Romania, Hungary, Serbia, Slovakia, Croatia, Bosnia Herzegovina and Macedonia) and Western Europe, including France, Spain, United Kingdom and Portugal. The document focuses just in the waste streams considered in the project, not providing details on other potential waste streams.

2 Pulp and Paper Industry in Balkan and central Europe

Central Europe is the most important region from the paper and board production point of view. Germany is the world's largest exporter and accounts for a quarter of the total European production and the whole region represents around the 40 % of the European production.

Austria

In Austria 24 mills produce pulp and paper. In 2015 they employed 7.878 persons. Following the trend of 2014, the total 2015 production volume increased by 2.0% and rose to 5M tonnes of paper. The total turnover stagnated at €3.8 billion in 2015 (+0.8%). Average prices for a tonne of paper dropped by €10 to €670 in 2015. Usually this is an alarming trend but in 2015 the prices of several input factors dropped as well. First, there was more supply on the energy market, which resulted in lower costs, and, second, the industrial roundwood market relaxed, which also led to reduced prices. Prices for the pre-product pulp dropped to €640 per tonne of reference grade Northern bleached softwood kraft (NBSK) in 2015. Around the turn of the year 2016 the price dropped further to €630 in response to the market decline.

(<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/country-info/statements/Austria2016.pdf>).

Germany

In a worldwide comparison, the German paper industry remains number four after China, the US and Japan and is the number one in Europe. Depending on the desired properties of new papers, their production is either based on mechanical pulp or chemical pulp as primary fibre or paper for recycling as secondary fibre. With a production of 23M tonnes paper and board per year the German industry generates a turnover of some 149 billion EUR and employ 40.000 people.

A look at the overall paper cycle shows, however, that fresh fibre has to be added from time to time for quality reasons. With a paper for recycling utilisation rate of 74 %, the German paper industry holds a top position in a recycling context.

In 2014, the German paper production stood for 25% of the European production. The corresponding pulp production was 7%.

(https://www.vdponline.de/fileadmin/Datensammlungen/Publikationen/Papier_kompakt_EN.pdf).

https://www.diw.de/documents/dokumentenarchiv/17/diw_01.c.534645.de/cs-pulp-and-paper.pdf

Poland

In 2015, 10 members companies of the Association of Polish Papermakers' Paper Section produced 3.37M tonnes of paper and board. It accounts for 78.8% of total production in Poland. The mills in Poland produced 1M tonnes of paper for printing purposes (1.8% down), 2,046,600 tonnes of packaging grades (5.5% up) and 323,600 tonnes of household and sanitary papers (7.4% up) (http://www.spp.pl/buletin_spp.php). The study (Budzyń et al, 2015) involved the following types of cellulose wastes: the rejects from recovered paper, deinking sludge, wastewater treatment sludge and the rejects from virgin pulps.

Italy

Italy is one of the largest producers in this segment in Europe. The Italian paper production accounted for 2% of the worldwide production of paper and 9% of the European production. The tissue paper market continues to be an important sector of the Italian paper industry. Among the CEPI members, the country has a share of 20% of total production (CEPI, 2017), putting it in second place just behind Germany (20.5%). In 2015, Italian suppliers produced 1.4M tonnes of household and sanitary paper, and apparent consumption increased by 1.2% to 680,000 tonnes, following two years of consecutive decline. The industrial process now regenerates more than 5M tonnes of waste paper (Livinec et. al, 2014).

Czech Republic

The pulp and paper industry is one of the most forward-looking branches of the Czech manufacturing industry. In relation to the European Union, Czech enterprises within this branch account for approximately 1 % of total EU output.

Pulp and paper products are used in all branches of the manufacturing industry, especially in printing and packing production. Different ratios of basic raw materials are used to make new paper and paperboard, i.e. new pulp (groundwood pulp and cellulose), waste and scrap paper and non-fibrous components (fillers, sizing agents, etc.). The usual composition in the Czech pulp and paper industry in 2005 was 51 % new pulp, 43 % waste paper, and 6 % other components (<http://www.pptgroup.se/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/061108-Pulp-Paper-CR-HU-SLOV.pdf>). The revenues of pulp, paper and paperboard manufacture in the Czech Republic reached approximately 1.09 billion U.S. dollars as it is referred in the previous document.

Slovakia Republic

Slovakia from a geographical point of view is a significantly diverse country, and with 41% forest coverage it ranks among the most forested countries in Europe (<http://www.esig.sk/en/industries/wood-processing---the-paper-industry>) Slovakian paper industry include for production and processing of pulp, paper, board, cardboxes, tissue and sanitary products and print. In 2014, production of wood pulp was 719 thousand and

in 2016 740.000 tonnes (<https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/timber/country-info/statements/slovakia2015.pdf>).

Slovenia

Slovene paper industry is small but very diverse. Niche production is the key of success. Paper industry is a traditional industry in Slovenia. Nowadays many of Slovene paper and paper converting companies are owned by foreigners. On average, 75% of products are exported, mainly to EU, but raw materials are importing from all over the world. Wood is a naturally renewable source and the base raw material for the production of fibers (wood pulp and cellulose) and paper.. Each year the use of wood from certified forests increases, which promotes sustainable forest management. The main raw material used in Slovene paper factories is waste paper (>55%). In Europe 66% of all the paper produced is collected (CEPI, 2016) while in Slovenia, at the moment, this percentage is around 58%. Pulp and paper industry plays an important role in the strategic program of Slovenia's transition to the circular economy (http://www.haag.veleposlanistvo.si/fileadmin/user_upload/dkp_29_vhg/docs/SI_selected_industries_avg_2010.pdf). The cost for landfilling in Slovenia is roughly 70-90 €/ton waste.

Hungary

The Hungarian pulp and paper industry is fairly small and growing slowly. Market is dominated by two companies. The Hungarian National Ministry for the Economy selected the Hungarian paper producer will for new investment, which is targeted to the construction of an integrated plant for the production of toilet paper <http://www.pptgroup.se/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/061108-Pulp-Paper-CR-HU-SLOV.pdf>.

TABLE 2. SUMMARY OF PULP AND PAPER INDUSTRIES PRODUCTION AND WASTE IN CENTRAL EUROPE

	Austria	Czech Republic	Germany	Slovakia	Italy	Poland	Slovenia	Hungary
Pulp production (mil. Tons)	2		2,5			1,154	0,14	
Paper production (mil. Tons)	5	0,75	22,6	0,61 (2005)	8,92	4,59	0,756	0,020
No. mills	24	8	20	4	17	9	6	2

Bark and wood residues (t)	377.002						30.000	
Primary sludge (t)	404.671		803.643 Deinking		280.000		70.000	
Secondary sludge (t)	129.821						2.000	
Slag and ash (t)	173.459				600.000		30.000	
Waste deposit (ext.) (t)	83.117							
Waste liquor (t)			4.505.678					
Rejects (t)							15.500	

The Balkan region does not have high impact on the European pulp and paper production in comparison with Central Europe, accounting for less than 1% of the European production. Because of that reason, detailed data about the production is not available for this region.

Croatia

The forest sector share in gross domestic product accounted for 1.4% in 2009 (0.5% furniture industry, 0.4% cellulose and paper industry and 0.5% wood and wood product industry). The amount of paper production is less of the 1% of the total European production (Technopolis, 2016).

Bosnia and Herzegovina

BiH is a country with the largest share of forest and the greatest diversity of forest types in the West-ern Balkans. The forests are one of the most important natural resources in the country Bosnia and Herzegovina has a long tradition and a good international reputation in the production of high quality wood products and furniture that meets the domestic, but the paper industry presents less than 1 % of the European production.

During 2015, the pulp, paper, and paperboard segment dominated the market and accounted for close to 45% of the market shares in terms of revenue. Products manufactured in this segment include uncoated and unbleached kraft liners, sack kraft paper, felt paper, grey paperboards, and fluting. This segment has also witnessed the

introduction of new product categories, such as paper for newsprint, paper and paperboards for photo-sensitive, heat sensitive, and electro-sensitive applications, and cellulose wadding for household and sanitary products, which will aid in the growth of this segment in the coming years (<https://www.technavio.com/report/bosnia-herzegovina-textile-fiber-and-composites-paper-manufacturing-market-bosnia-and>).

Macedonia

Macedonia's industries are centred around Skopje. Steel and chemical production, along with buses, textiles, food processing, tobacco, furniture, and ceramics are important industries. Paper industry is not one of the important industries and the production is less than 1 % of the European production (<http://www.nationsencyclopedia.com/Europe/Macedonia-INDUSTRY.html#ixzz549hgDd19>).

Serbia

The production of Serbian and Montenegro pulp and paper production was 0.506M tonnes with 11 paper mills. Main raw material is wood (<https://www.paperonweb.com/Serbia.htm>). The amount of paper production is less of the 1% of the total European production.

Romania

In the last decades, the surface of Romanian forests decreased due to an intensive harvesting and, as a consequence, the price of pulpwood significantly increased. In the same time, the regulations for environmental protection were successively hardened in Romania, so that all chemical pulp mills were closed for economic and environmental reasons. In these circumstances, Romanian paper producers shifted to recovered paper as raw material. This decision is in accordance with trends of European paper sector, where recovered, paper continuously strengthened its position as raw material for paper industry. Romania has 9 pulp and paper mills companies (<http://www.tissueworldmagazine.com/country-report/romania-overall-weakness-offset-by-strength-in-ff/>). The production is strictly oriented towards two paper grades of low or medium quality like papers for corrugated board (65%) and sanitary papers also called tissue papers (35%). In Romania, recovered paper is only used as a raw material in the paper sector. Unfortunately, in Romania, large quantities of waste paper still end up in the landfills.

TABLE 3. BALKAN PPI

	Romania	Croatia	Boznia and Herzegovina	Macedonia	Serbia
Paper production (M. T)	0,3	0,247	<1	<1	<1
No. mills		2	3	1	11

3 Pulp and Paper Industry in the Nordic countries

The Nordic countries are Denmark, Norway, Finland, Sweden and Iceland. Of these five only Finland, Sweden and to some extent, Norway has pulp and paper industries.

Finland

Finland has a long tradition of PPI and accounts for two-thirds of the total production value of the Finnish forest industry. Of the total paper and board production in Europe, Finland accounts for 11% with an annual production of 10 million tonnes. The Finnish PPI has had a paradigm shift during the last five years when it comes to waste stream handling. The waste that goes to landfill has been reduced by ca 50% during these years and has been possible due to advanced circular economy. Detailed information about the improvements are not official, but the Finnish forest industry organisation publish the main research topics as valorisation of ash as a material for the construction industry and in earthworks as well as large scale use of sludge in production of fertilizers.

Sweden

Like Finland, Sweden has a long tradition of forest industry and PPI. The production is roughly the same in these two countries in pulp, paper and board. Sweden is the third largest exporter of forest-based products in the world. Despite this large production, only 1% of the forest is felled annually and the growth outpaces felling.

Norway

The Norwegian PPI is quite small compared to the neighbouring countries. The main production is paper from mechanical pulp with an annual quantity of 1.5 million tonnes.

Nordic Countries summary

The Nordic countries is quite open with statistical data of the PPI, however, the specific cost for waste handling is far more discrete and the numbers showing the cost below in table 4 is mainly showing the range rather than exact figures. The distribution of the landfilled waste streams is from the Finnish forest industry organisation and, based on that the raw material and the production is roughly the same in Sweden, the Swedish waste on a national level is estimated and presented in table 4. The estimation has been verified with data on some of the waste streams, such as green liquor dregs. However, as discussed above, the data is mainly showing the ranges of the costs and amounts rather than exact numbers. This distribution is seen in figure 1 below. From this data it is quite clear that it is the pulp mills that produce the largest amount of landfilled waste as green liquor is a waste stream from both sulphate(kraft) and the sulphite process.

FIGUR 1. ESTIMATED DISTRIBUTION OF LANDFILLED WASTE IN FINLAND AND SWEDEN.

TABLE 4. SUMMARY TABLE OF THE NORDIC COUNTRIES.

<i>Country</i>	<i>Finland</i>	<i>Sweden</i>	<i>Norway</i>
Paper mills	17	29	3
Paperboard mills	14	10	0
Pulp mills	19	33	7
Chemical pulp mill. tonnes/year	7.45	9.25	0.16
Mechanical and semi mechanical mill. tonnes/year	3.45	4.56	1.268
Total landfill waste tonnes/Year	68500	150103	25000
Green liquor dregs Tonnes/year	46854	105072	n.d
Green liquor dregs € /tonnes	n.d	70	n.d
Deinking €/tonnes	n.d	n.d	n.d
Deinking waste tonnes/year	3220	7505	n.d
Lime mud €/tonnes	n.d	40	n.d
Lime mud tonnes/year	3288	7505	n.d
Sludge from wwt* €/tonnes	n.d	60	n.d
Sludge from wwt* tonnes/year	1165	3002	n.d
Fibre and coating sludge €/tonnes	n.d	60	n.d
Fibre and coating sludge tonnes/year	343	751	n.d
Other waste €/tonnes	n.d	60	n.d
Other waste tonnes/year	5069	8106	5000
Wood waste €/tonnes	n.d	60	n.d
Wood waste tonnes/year	69	150	n.d
Ashes €/tonnes	n.d	110	n.d
Ashes tonnes/year	8494	18012	20000

* wwt = Waste water treatment

4 Western Europe; Spanish, British, Portuguese and French markets

Spain

Spain is the sixth European producer, with a production of 7.9 million tonnes of paper and board (8,7 % of the European production) in 2016 (ASPAPEL, <http://www.aspapel.es/el-sector/descripcion>), generated in 10 pulp mills and 71 paper mills. The industry is quite widespread around the north half of the country.

The pulp production is varied, coming from recycled fibres and virgin fibres from chemical pulp mills; consequently, the waste production shows also a wide variety. It is remarkable the relevance of short fibres from eucalyptus as raw materials and the high recycling rate, the second highest in Europe just behind Germany.

The last available report on Spanish waste production in the PPI (ASPAPEL, 2007) identified a global non-hazardous waste production of 1.45 million tonnes out of 1.5 total million tonnes, with the following distribution: paper rejects (30%), fibre sludge (21%), deinking paper sludge (17 %) and wastewater treatment sludge (17%). These figures have changed during the last years thanks to the implementation of different energy valorisation alternatives and the reduction of companies and industrial facilities.

United Kingdom

The United Kingdom produced 4 million tonnes in 2015, accounting for 4,3 % of the European production. The sector consists of 12 mills distributed along the country although with some concentration in the middle – north part of England. The rest of the sector are different paper and board mills that process pulp. A 70 % of the total production is concentrated in 7 mills.

Almost the entire sector recycles fibres from recycled paper and board and a few percentage comes from domestic woodpulp. The sector imports the great majority of the woodpulp.

UK has a high recycling rate, recovering each year around eight million tonnes of paper and board, being reused in the country less than 3.3 million tonnes. The rest of them is exported, mainly to China.

Summarising, the local sector employs mainly recycled fibres and consequently the waste production is related to sludge. However, UK has an extended coverage of waste-to-energy plants in their facilities so most of the sludge is valorised for energy production in both, internal facilities or external partners to produce electricity. Therefore, the waste disposal is low and the ashes are one of the most common residues.

France

France produced almost eight million tonnes of paper and board in 2016, accounting for almost the 9 % of the European production. The sector is composed of 75 companies and 85 paper mills. There are eight pulp mills corresponding with two mechanical mills, five chemical mills and one recycling paper mill.

Around 60 % of the French production takes place in the Northeast and Southern part of the country, in accordance with the forest industry distribution.

Due to the variety of the French PPI, all type of waste streams considered in the project can be found, although there is a clear predominance of the chemical pulp production. The occurrence of waste-to-energy plants in different mills implies the production of different type of ashes, including those coming from paper rejects and/or deinking paper sludge, considered in the project.

The available resources in terms of waste can be easily identified thanks to the degree of accuracy of the French Pollutant Release Transfer Register (<http://www.georisques.gouv.fr/dossiers/irep/form-dechet#/>), which details the type of waste produced and the rate of valorisation (disposed/recycled) for each case. This information easily allows a potential interested party to know the waste availability per

producer. The platform also allows to search by type of waste (LER code). **Portugal** Portugal's leading manufacturers of paper pulp, paper and cardboard, are represented in roughly 10 companies (all members of the Portuguese Association of the Paper Industry – CELPA), corresponding to about 90% of the country's output in paper and cardboard, processing about 8 million cubic meters of wood per year, planting approximately 200,000 hectares of forest.

In 2016, the sales volume in the pulp and paper sector (represented by CELPA associates) was €2.54 billion, corresponding to 1.37% of Portugal's PIB. Meaning that the total amount of eucalyptus wood consumed by the pulp and paper industry, in 2016, was 7,795 thousand cubic meters (wood without bark).

Portuguese pulp and paper industry represents nearly 6% of the country's exports of goods. Portugal is Europe's leading producer of uncoated fine papers, accounting for nearly 60% of office paper exports from Europe to the rest of the world. Portugal is currently the leading European producer, of Bleached Eucalyptus Pulp (BEKP).

The Portuguese production of virgin fibre pulp, in 2016, was fixed at 2,729 thousand tons, where 94% of this value relates to eucalyptus pulp, and the remaining to pine pulp. The consumption of pulp for paper production in 2016 was 1,785 thousand tons.

The consumption of pulp for paper production totalised, in 2016, 1,785.2 thousand tons, also, the total production of paper and board in 2016 was 2,300.2 thousand tons. 70.9% of the paper production goes to uncoated wood-free paper and board (UWF), 19.0% goes

to corrugated card covers, 4.8% to tissue paper, 3.4% to papers and cards for packaging and 1.8% goes to other papers types.

Portugal has exported in 2016 pulp to paper to 23 countries, being the Community market, including Portugal, the main destination for national paper pulp, accounting for 78.6% of sales, followed by the Middle East, Asia and Oceania with 20.9%.

Regarding environmental indicators, CELPA associates, have reported in 2016, a production of around 80 million cubic meters of treated (primary and secondary) liquid effluent. Concerning the solid residues, in 2016, the sludge's represented a total of round 390 thousand tons, while ashes, slag, dust and other boiler waste, represented around 90 thousand ton. Other solid residues totalised around 10 thousand ton.

Considering only The Navigator Company position, 200 thousand tons of bark and 28 thousand tons of sawdust are produced annually, together with 16 thousand tons of primary sludge. (http://www.celpe.pt/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Boletim_WEB.pdf)

TABLE 5. SUMMARY TABLE OF THE WESTERN COUNTRIES

Country	Spain	France	Portugal	UK
Paper and paperboard mills	71	85	10	12
Pulp mills	10	8	8	8
Chemical pulp mill. tonnes/year	1.676	1.720	2.729	0.3
Mechanical and semi mechanical mill. T/year	0		0	0
Total landfill waste tonnes/Year			100,000	62,704
Green liquor dregs Tonnes/year	20,822.2	14,076	54,460	-
Deinking waste tonnes/year	128,647	14,278	20,000	
Lime mud tonnes/year	98,879.6	45,595	45,000	-
Sludge from wwt tonnes/year	222,309	75,412	83,000	
Fibre and coating sludge tonnes/year	304,500			
Other waste tonnes/year			10,000	
Wood waste tonnes/year			378,000	-
Ashes tonnes/year	58.195	56,570	-	21,090*

(*) Estimated value from the main producers. Some available data points out that the estimated amount could be as high as 125.000 tonnes yearly (Defra, 2012).

5 Preliminary cost analysis in Europe

Results from the waste stream analysis presented in the previous sections show that wastes produced by the Pulp and Paper industries across Europe present a great valorisation potential, at least from a quantitative point of view. To confirm it, a detailed techno-economic analysis is necessary to **identified and characterised the impact of the new valorisation streams on waste management processes**. Additionally, the overall economic viability of the project shall be evaluated considering the whole ecosystem, namely the gains for the waste producers in the PPI and the waste re-user(s) in other industries.

However, and as long as circular models are not yet designed, negotiated and implemented, the European Pulp and Paper industries remain responsible for the management of their waste. On the one hand, **waste management activities are increasingly complex and expensive**. In the world, solid waste management costs is expected to jump from \$205.4 billion in 2012 to about \$375.5 billion in 2025, mainly due to waste volumes increasing even faster than urbanisation rates (World Bank Group, 2012). In addition, and focusing on the European Union, the waste legislation is increasingly bidding, whether it is at EU or at local levels. On the other hand, the implementation of new valorisation streams may require **initial investments, more complex day-to-day logistics** and potentially higher operational costs for the European Pulp and Paper industries. Consequently, the successful deployment of innovative circular models relies first on the ability to **convince stakeholders of the EU PPI that they will benefit** in a significant manner from such valorisation streams.

This preliminary cost analysis aims at identifying **most important parameters** to be considered for the development of a cost evaluation model. To that end, the study intends to identify whether EU Member States share common models or methodologies and collect data available in the literature to provide **a first range of value for these parameters**. Results of this study will be used as a basis in Task 8.1 to further analyse the transition from existing processes to the circular economy processes.

Interference with waste reduction programs

Stakeholders of the PPI perform internal actions to reduce the amount of waste generated before considering the valorisation of a waste in other industries. Consequently, the introduction of new valorisation streams may have an impact on the economic aspects of the current measures. Similarly, modifications applied to current measures may also have an impact on the economic viability of the new valorisation streams. Therefore, potential interferences shall be identified to ensure an effective analysis.

Five main measures are listed in the EU waste legislation (The European Parliament & Council, 2008) whose definitions are given hereafter:

- **Prevention** means, among other aspects¹, measures taken before a substance, material or product has become waste, that reduce the quantity of waste, including through the re-use of products or the extension of the life span of products;
- **Reuse of waste** means any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived;
- **Recycling of waste** means any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes;
- **Recovery of waste** means any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials;
- **Disposal of waste** means any operation which is not recovery (Eurostat, 2018).

The major principle described in EU policy for waste management is the **waste management hierarchy**. Indeed, waste prevention and management measures shall be applied in a given order to ensure an efficient approach (The European Parliament & Council, 2008). Thus, applied strategies shall firstly prevent the generation of waste. Whenever prevention reaches its limits, waste shall be in this order, reused, recycled or recovered. The latest options cover the use to produce energy and, as a final resort, the disposal (The Regional Environmental Center, 2007). The waste hierarchy is illustrated in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.:**

¹ A part of the definition was removed due to the non-hazardous nature of PPI waste.

FIGURE 1. WASTE HIERARCHY (WORLD BANK GROUP, 2012)

The new valorisation streams studied within the Paperchain project all fall into the definition of recovery of waste. Consequently, they are located downstream all other waste diversion measures and **do not impact associated costs or benefits of potential programs already in place**, meaning:

- Waste reduction rate and associated costs/benefits
- Reuse rate and associated costs/benefits
- Recycling rate and associated costs/benefits

Oppositely, **these programs may impact the economic viability of the new waste streams** by reducing or increasing the volume of waste currently intended to be disposed. However, and within the scope of this preliminary cost analysis, it is considered that all other measures have reached maturity, leading to a process with a constant volume of waste. Regarding waste disposal options, the implementation of valorisation streams would have an economic impact that shall be further assessed.

Cost estimation models for waste management

A cost estimation model for waste management processes is necessary to evaluate the economic potential of new valorisation streams. It identifies all costs associated to each step of the process and provide a range of value for all parameters. However, the literature review performed within the scope of this study **did not identify any official cost estimation model in the EU legislation.**

Instead, the regulation 1013/2006/EC on shipments of waste (European Parliament, 2006) was analysed. It aims at protecting the environment in the context of a waste shipment and establishes rules to regulate waste transports. Article 6 of the regulation deals with specific waste shipments that shall be associated with a financial guarantee or equivalent insurance. This guarantee aims at covering potential extra costs due to a transport, recovery or disposal activity that cannot be completed or was performed illegally. As mentioned in the text, this financial guarantee shall cover all costs related to the waste management, namely:

- Costs of **transport**;
- Costs of **recovery** or **disposal**;
- Costs of **storage** for 90 days.

Therefore, the above list can be considered as exhaustive and the four costs can be used as a basis to build a cost estimation model. However, the regulation does not provide any further detail on how to estimate these costs nor deliver a model to be applied by EU Member States.

An academic work dedicated to the estimation of logistics costs in case of industrial waste management (Janusz Grabara and Mariana Man, 2014) also based its research studies on these 4 costs. The following mathematical formula was used to breakdown the cost:

$$C_{TOT} = C_S + C_T + C_R + C_D$$

Where:

- C_{TOT} – total logistics costs of waste management;
- C_T – transport costs;
- C_S – storage costs;
- C_R – recovery costs;
- C_D – disposal costs.

In the absence of a cost evaluation model commonly shared at EU level, this equation is used as a basis for the preliminary cost analysis.

Breakdown of most relevant parameters

The above-mentioned cost breakdown has been further detailed thanks to a literature review. However, and as acknowledged by European bodies, few data are available on the cost of waste management at EU level (European Parliament, 2015).

In September 2016, the European Commission released a compilation document on the calculation of the financial guarantee for shipments of waste set (European Commission, 2016). It results from an analysis carried out in 2010 to assess current practices. In total 20 Member States, 12 German Länder, 8 Spanish regions and 26 French region authorities provided data on this calculation. This document and other studies have been used to detail how the different costs are calculated and to identify whether there is a preferred approach or value.

Storage costs

Storage costs result from the storage of waste by the PPI requiring space, management, etc. The analysis carried out by the EU (European Commission, 2016) tends to demonstrate that storage costs are mostly described based on the following format:

$$C_s = S \cdot m$$

Where:

- C_s – storage costs (€)
- m – the mass of waste handled (tons)
- S – constant (€/ton)

The C_s constant depends on 3 parameters:

- The nature of the waste stream (hazardous or non-hazardous)
- The nature of the storage (indoor or outdoor)
- The state of the waste (liquid or solid)

Storage varies between € 15/ton and € 70/ton for non-hazardous resp. solid waste and € 70/ton - € 350/ton for hazardous resp. liquid waste. The following table shows values for non-hazardous wastes²:

² Storage costs are higher for hazardous wastes but they were not considered as they are not part of the scope of the PAPERCHAIN project.

Country	Type of disposal or waste	Cost per tonne
Austria	non-hazardous wastes	40 €/ton
	non-hazardous wastes (outdoor storage)	35 €/ton
Wallonia	non-hazardous wastes (indoor storage)	70 €/ton
	non-hazardous wastes (outdoor storage)	35 €/ton
Luxembourg	non-hazardous wastes (indoor storage)	70 €/ton
	non-hazardous wastes (solid)	47€/ton
Poland	non-hazardous wastes (liquid)	117€/ton

TABLE 5. EXAMPLES OF COSTS OF STORAGE FOR 90 DAYS IN SEVERAL EU MEMBER STATES

Recovery costs

This type of cost results from the process conducted to recover the waste, so that it can be used another time. The analysis carried out by the EU (European Commission, 2016) tends to demonstrate that recovery costs can be described using the following format:

$$C_R = R \cdot m$$

Where:

- C_R – recovery costs (€)
- m – the mass of waste handled (ton)
- R – constant (€/ton)

However, the value of the R constant shall be defined on a case-by-case basis. It depends on:

- Legal requirements from the new use (which may lead to additional treatment to wastes)
- Who carry the cost (agreements must be found between the waste producer and re-user)

Transport costs

Transport costs refer to the cost generated by the transport of waste between their point of generation and the point in where they are disposed or recovered. The analysis carried out by the EU has shown that transport costs are mostly described with the following formula (European Commission, 2016):

$$C_T = T \cdot m \cdot x$$

Where:

- C_T – transport costs (€)
- m – the mass of waste handled (tons)
- x – number of kilometres travelled (km)
- T – constant (€/ton/km)

For non-hazardous³ waste, **transport cost ranges from € 0.09 to € 0.17/ €/Km/Ton.**

Disposal costs

After waste generation, storage, recovery attempts and transport, remaining waste can be disposed on landfills. The analysis carried out by the EU (European Commission, 2016) tends to demonstrate that disposal costs are mostly described based on the following format:

$$C_D = D \cdot m$$

Where:

- C_D – disposal costs (€)
- m – the mass of waste handled (tons)
- D – constant (€/ton)

If the formula to calculate disposal cost is quite simple, costs themselves vary widely from one location to another, or even from one mill to another, due to local fees and local

³ Similarly to storage costs, transport costs are higher for hazardous wastes. However, they were not considered as they are not part of the scope of the PAPERCHAIN project.

demand. In addition, some PPI have their own internal landfills which might be a key competitive advantage. As a result, no information can be found in the literature on the range of costs for such internal constructions.

As a first estimation, several sources were compared to provide a range of disposal costs in countries of interest for PAPERCHAIN. First, the World Bank Group explains that the more developed is a country, the more expensive are the disposal costs, as shown on **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** (World Bank Group, 2012):

Estimated Solid Waste Management Costs by Disposal Method ¹

	Low Income Countries	Lower Mid Inc Countries	Upper Mid Inc Countries	High Income Countries
Income (GNI/capita)	<\$876	\$876-3,465	\$3,466-10,725	>\$10,725
Waste Generation (tonnes/capita/yr)	0.22	0.29	0.42	0.78
Collection Efficiency (percent collected)	43%	68%	85%	98%
Cost of Collection and Disposal (US\$/tonne)				
Collection ²	20-50	30-75	40-90	85-250
Sanitary Landfill	10-30	15-40	25-65	40-100
Open Dumping	2-8	3-10	NA	NA
Composting ³	5-30	10-40	20-75	35-90
Waste -to-Energy Incineration ⁴	NA	40-100	60-150	70-200
Anaerobic Digestion ⁵	NA	20-80	50-100	65-150

NOTE: This is a compilation table from several World Bank documents, discussions with the World Bank's Thematic Group on Solid Waste, Carl Bar-tone and other industry and organizational colleagues. Costs associated with uncollected waste—more than half of all waste generated in low-income countries—are not included.

FIGURE 2 – ESTIMATED SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT COSTS BY DISPOSAL METHOD (WORLD BANK GROUP, 2012)

All countries within the scope of the PAPERCHAIN project are high income countries and therefore, **disposal cost ranges from 40€ to 100€** according to the World Bank Group.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OCDE) constitutes another source of information through its Policy INstruments for the Environment (PINE) database. The PINE database is freely accessible and contains qualitative and quantitative information on environmentally related taxes, fees and charges, tradable permits, deposit-refund systems, environmentally motivated subsidies and voluntary approaches. The following table presents types of disposal or waste and their cost per ton in countries or areas of interest for PAPERCHAIN.

TABLE 6. DISPOSAL COST FOR WASTE (OECD, 2017)

Country	Type of disposal or waste	Cost per ton
Spain (Valencia)	Non recoverable waste	3€
Spain (Murcia)	Recoverable waste	5€
Portugal	Landfill	6.39€
Spain (Cantabria)	N/C	7€
Spain (Extremadura)	N/C	10€
Spain (La Rioja)	N/C	12€
Spain (Castilla y Leon)	Non recoverable waste	15€
	Recoverable waste	20€
Sweden	Landfill	52.79€

According to the PINE database, **disposal cost ranges from 3€ to 53€.**

Finally, a third document from the European Cooperation for Science and Technology (COST) indicates that in some European countries, “**waste disposal fees have already reached the level of 150€/ton**” (COST, 2010).

Result of the preliminary cost analysis

Two scenarios are considered to characterise the impact of new valorisation streams on waste management processes:

- **Scenario 1** represents the **current model**, i.e. without new valorisation streams
- **Scenario 2** represents the situation in which a **circular model** is implemented

Therefore, the impact on costs induced by the transition from the current model to a circular model by the implementation of new valorisation streams can be described as followed:

$$\Delta C_{TOT} = C_1 - C_2 \quad (1)$$

Where:

- ΔC_{TOT} – total cost variation
- C_1 – Total cost of scenario 1
- C_2 – Total cost of scenario 2

Considering the high-level formula presented in the section “Preliminary cost analysis in Europe” of this report to breakdown the total costs of waste management:

$$C_{TOT} = C_S + C_R + C_T + C_D \quad (2)$$

Where:

- C_{TOT} – total logistics costs of waste management;
- C_S – storage costs, $C_S = S \cdot m$
- C_R – recovery costs, $C_R = R \cdot m$
- C_T – transport costs, $C_T = T \cdot m \cdot x$
- C_D – disposal costs, $C_D = D \cdot m$

And combining equations (1) and (2), the impact on costs can be expressed as followed:

$$\Delta C_{TOT} = (C_{S1} + C_{R1} + C_{T1} + C_{D1}) - (C_{S2} + C_{R2} + C_{T2} + C_{D2})$$

The aim of this preliminary cost analysis is to study key parameters that have the highest impact on the economic viability, not to develop an accurate cost estimation model. Therefore, several hypotheses⁴ have been made to simplify the above equation. The first two concern recovery and disposal costs:

- Hypothesis 1: there is **no recovery cost in scenario 1**. The lack of data from the field prevents from identifying recovery measures already started by PPI stakeholders. Therefore, it is considered that no recovery measure has been implemented on the given waste streams so far $\rightarrow C_{R1} = 0$
- Hypothesis 2: there is **no disposal cost in scenario 2**. The large range of waste streams studied within the scope of PAPERCHAIN does not allow to define the

⁴ These hypotheses could be challenged in task 8.1 to develop a more accurate approach, using interviews with stakeholders and data from the project case studies.

percentage of waste that is not compliant for recovery. Therefore, it is considered for that study that the total amount of the given waste stream can be recovered
→ $C_{D2} = 0$

Based on hypotheses 1 and 2, the previous equation becomes:

$$\Delta C_{TOT} = (C_{S1} + C_{T1} + C_{D1}) - (C_{S2} + C_{R2} + C_{T2})$$

Furthermore, two more hypotheses have been made on the breakdown of storage and transport costs:

- Hypothesis 3: The **S constant of the storage cost breakdown (Cs)** remains the same in scenario 1 and 2. The literature review has shown that the S constant usually depends on the nature of the waste (hazardous or non-hazardous) and the type of storage (indoor or outdoor). For this study, it is considered that the nature of the waste does not change from one scenario to another and that the same type of storage is used → $S1=S2=S$
- Hypothesis 4: The **T constant of the transport cost breakdown (Cr)** remains the same in scenario 1 and 2. The literature review has shown that the T constant usually depends on the nature of the transported waste (hazardous or non-hazardous). For the study, and as PAPERCHAIN focuses on non-hazardous waste only, it is considered that the nature of the waste does not change from one scenario to another → $T1=T2=T$

According to the two last hypotheses and based on cost breakdowns presented in the section "Breakdown of most relevant parameters" of this report, the equation becomes:

$$\Delta C_{TOT} = S \cdot (m_1 - m_2) + T \cdot (m_1 \cdot x_1 - m_2 \cdot x_2) + D \cdot m_1 - R \cdot m_2$$

Where:

- x – number of kilometres travelled (km)
- m – the mass of waste handled (tons)
- T, S, D and R – constants

Finally, a fifth hypothesis was made on the mass of waste handled. Indeed, it has been considered that there is **no mass variation between scenario 1 and 2** ($m_1 = m_2 = m$). Based on these hypothesis, the equation becomes:

$$\Delta C_{TOT} = [(D - R) + T \cdot (x_1 - x_2)] \cdot m$$

Where:

- D ranges from 3 to 150€/ton
- T ranges from 0.09 to 0.017€/Km/Ton
- R (in €/ton) must be defined on a case by case basis

First and foremost, $\Delta C_{TOT} > 0$ is a necessary condition to ensure the economic viability of the transition to a circular model, from the PPI point of view. It could be further illustrated by the following formula:

$$(D - R) + T \cdot (x_1 - x_2) > 0$$

It comes as no surprise that the cost difference between disposal and recovery options (in €/ton) is paramount for the economic viability. Therefore, **the economic viability of new valorisation streams can be expected to be higher in countries that set high fees to disposal solutions**, usually most developed countries (World Bank Group, 2012). However, further researches on the costs of local recovery options shall be done to ensure economic benefits for the PPI.

The equation also reflects well the principle of proximity that states that wastes should be used as close as possible to the source (The Regional Environmental Center, 2007). Accordingly, **the implementation of circular model shall be highly questioned when dealing with situations where the recovery site is much further than the disposal site**. For instance, the economic interest of implementing such valorisation streams seems very low for PPI stakeholders that have their on-site landfill. Nevertheless, the importance of the distance differential shall be balanced by the low values of the T constant compared to the D constant (175 to 1700 times lower according to the literature).

Finally, $\Delta C_{TOT} > 0$ is a necessary but not sufficient condition to obtain the economic viability. On the one hand, the equation highlights the importance of the mass parameter (m) and the more quantity of waste handled, the higher the economic benefits. **Therefore, the economic viability of new valorisation streams can be expected to be higher for large mills**. On the other hand, the economic viability shall also be studied from the point of view of the industrial that will reuse the waste. To that end, the cost of current raw materials shall be compared to the cost of waste recovery. **The economic interest shall be validated from both side to consider the implementation of a circular model**.

6 Conclusion

European PPI waste production has been investigated and summarized in this report. Typical for this type of data is the **large variation** between the producers due to different capacity, processes and raw material. However, **on a national level the data is representative** for the investigated countries. The amount of waste that goes to landfill is **not linear** to the amount of produced pulp when comparing the different countries and the **potential for further valorization is huge**. A very good example is Finland which has extremely low amount of waste that goes to landfill.

The preliminary cost analysis **did not identify a common cost evaluation model** used at EU level for waste management but **a list of costs to be mandatorily taken into account** (European Commission, 2016). In addition, it appears that **EU Members States often apply similar models but with various values for parameters** (European Commission, 2016). Regarding data, **there is few available in the literature** due to the strategic nature of such information. Available data show a high variability from one location to another due to the influence of several parameters (local fees, local demand, etc.). Finally, the preliminary cost analysis resulted in two main observations. Firstly, circular models should be implemented in priority for **large mills that do not have their own landfills and operate in countries/regions that set high disposal fees**. Secondly, the identification of **partners as close as possible to PPI stakeholders** is key to ensure the economic viability. The results of this preliminary cost analysis will be as a basis for the transition assessment to be performed in the scope of Task 8.1.

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